

The Invisible Labor in Abakaliki Rice Mill

Author: Immaculeta Eleje Enya

Affiliation: PhD Student (Industrial Sociology), University of Ibadan

Date: February 2026

Abstract

During a fieldwork at a rice mill in Abakaliki, southeastern Nigeria, I observed older women recovering residual rice grains from discarded husk heaps. This labor is entirely feminized, unrecognized, and exposes women to occupational risks such as dust inhalation and long hours. Yet it extends the rice value chain beyond what formal production metrics capture, highlighting critical questions about gendered labor and invisibility in informal economies.

Observation / Field Note

At the Abakaliki rice mill, everyone notices the machines grinding, men lifting heavy sacks, and traders negotiating prices.

But at the far edge of the mill, older women sit at the base of a mountain of discarded rice husk. Dust in their nostrils, they carefully sift out tiny grains left behind. Some take the rice home to feed their families; others sell it to people who cannot afford clean, polished rice.

This work is invisible, risky, and entirely feminized. Yet these women quietly sustain households and create value from what the system discards.

The husk pyramid illustrates a broader reality: development produces measurable output, but inequality determines who depends on what is considered waste. In informal agricultural economies, the most essential actors are often the least visible.

Older women recovering rice grains from discarded husk at Abakaliki rice mill (photo by author).

Keywords: Gender, Informal Economy, Agriculture, Fieldwork, Nigeria, Industrial Sociology